

BIBLIOGRAPHY PROSPECTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF RENEWING UZBEKISTAN

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6549209>

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"Library and information activities"

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqola Yangilanayotgan O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida Kutubxona-axborot faoliyati xususan bibliografiya sohasida amalga oshirilayotgan islohatlar va ularning samarali natijalari haqida yozilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Bibliografiya, axborot, terminalogiya, "Bibeardy", funksiya, elektron kutubxona, elektron katalog, tendensiya, sivilizatsiya, integratsiya, Ma'lumotlar bazasi.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье речь идет о проводимых реформах в сфере библиотечно-информационной деятельности, особенно в сфере библиографии, и их эффективных результатах в развитии современного Узбекистана.*

Ключевые слова: *Библиография, информация, терминология, Биберды, функция, электронная библиотека, электронный каталог, направление, цивилизация, интеграция, База данных.*

Annotation: *This article is about the ongoing reforms in the field of library and information activities, especially in the field of bibliography, and their effective results in the development of modern Uzbekistan.*

Key words: *Bibliography, information, terminology, Bibeardy, function, electronic library, electronic catalog, trend, civilization, integration, Database.*

Bibliography is one of the most important components of science and social relations. The level of cognitive-communication processes also depends on its state level. These forces strive to constantly increase the volume of bibliographic resources, to improve their quality, to use all available resources to increase the number of users, to make the most of all potential bibliographic opportunities. "Bibeardy" is an ancient Greek word. It literally means, "Accounting software". In the 5th century BC. In Greece, the Bibles began to call people who would rewrite books.

All types of bibliographic activities, regardless of their departmental connections, are expected to include student composition, funding, and profile factors. It can be said that bibliographic activity is carried out in all the main directions of its work, as it is carried out with the participation of the bibliographic unit, through the "function" of the library. In recent years, this "cross-cutting function" has been associated with the introduction of computer technology in bibliographic units. This opened up remote access to local and international information resources. A bibliographic process combines library and research and information technology to meet the rapidly evolving information needs of both scientists and professionals and other populations.

The bibliographic requirements for all types of libraries, especially for large scientific growing bibliographic activities, are constantly increasing, primarily due to the quantitative and qualitative changes that occur in the documentary communication system. Improving the quality and efficiency of the bibliographic work of the library is always a need for acceleration, it requires its organization. The effectiveness and quality of the work of the library depends in many respects on the correct formation of bibliographic activities and the contribution of his company to the Information Process.

How to "manage" with book wealth? - This question has long been a concern for people. The advantages and disadvantages of the collections and the best works have been created. For example, in ancient Russia, people still read books with x1. They began to compile shitomatology and rewrote shitomatology called llamores.

It was already very common in the ancient world of the library, meaning that ministers could not remember all the papyrus inscriptions or clay tablets - their number had reached thousands. Libraries inventory has adopted a recovery that turns it into modern map data. Over time, library catalogs have included various lists, indexes, book reviews, and articles in library catalogs. All of them were commonly referred to as bibliography and modern terminology, which is a bibliographic benefit.

With the fall of the ancient world, the book culture he created was killed, and the word "bibliography" disappeared. They remembered the printing press soon after the Renaissance began. Bibliographers sometimes began to call typographers. In the first half of the 17th century, French scholars Gabrielle Codews and Louis Jacob first used the word "bibliography" to refer to the word "literature". Then he got a broader word. Later, during a long period of historical practice, the use of the term

"bibliography" acquired specific features of the plural. The most important and stable values can be distinguished:

- 1) "Bibliography" as a separate bibliographic work, as an index of bibliographic information;
- 2) "Bibliography" as any collection of periodicals or a collection of bibliographic works allocated by the bibliography;
- 3) "Bibliography" science, topics and tasks, formed at different times and by different authors;
- 4) As a field of practical (or scientific and practical) activity as "Bibliography" and as a field of practical activity on preparation of bibliographic services of information consumers;
- 5) "Bibliography" as the broadest collective concept covering all of the above and other bibliographic phenomena.

The last two definitions predominate in modern bibliographic science and practice.

In the historical complication of the bibliographic activity of its tasks and functions, organizational forms and techniques are entering into a wide and diverse range of bibliographic activities, inevitably beginning. There are two main processes of bibliographic activity: bibliography and bibliographic services.

In recent years, there has been a desire in the system of bibliographic terminology to clearly define the term "bibliography". At this value, "bibliography" as a system of various activities (practical, scientific, administrative), ensures the processing of bibliographic information in society.

Thus, the term "bibliography", the management and integration of the system of bibliographic terminology, is incompatible with any element of this system. In particular, the concepts of "Bibliography" and "Bibliographic activity" are being identified. The concept of "bibliographic activity" is one of the most common concepts of the library. In the 70s and 80s, it had a theoretical basis in terms of reference to bibliography, which gained categorical importance in the literature and among those used before it. It was related to the basic concept of "Bibliography". Concepts should be considered as a natural and continuous process in the development of bibliographic practice and the development of science, enriching new possibilities for explaining new bibliographic phenomena.

Many authors have considered "bibliography" and "bibliographic activity" as synonyms. In many cases, these concepts are not always

replaced, which is not always the case, which indicates some semantic differences, their evolution.

All the different materials about bibliographic activities are combined into two approaches, which can be defined as restrictive and expansive. The first is related to understanding it as a bibliographic practice, and it has long been Dominant. The second approach is an integral part of bibliographic activities, covering all the diversity of these bibliographic events. The traditional interpretation of the most complete forms adopted in dichotomy is bibliography (a field of scientific and practical activity) and bibliographers (as a science in this field). Thus, bibliographic activities are equivalent to practice, and bibliography is understood as a “scientific and practical activity,” so bibliographic activities are equivalent to bibliography.

The expansion approach includes bibliographic activities, bibliographic events, as well as bibliography in the broadest sense. Terms work as synonyms, and one of them is redundant in terms of scientific terminology.

Bibliographic activity is defined as the area of activity to meet the demand for bibliographic information, i.e., the scientific, educational and pedagogical components remain outside the boundaries, while the research, teaching and pedagogical components remain. At the same time, the concept of activity summarizes the unity of science and practice, knowledge and change. Considering bibliographic activities only practical, my content in this category is limited. You can conclude that the concepts of “bibliography” and “bibliographic activity” are the most common in terms of maintenance.

This is one of the most difficult and problematic in the modern Bible. There are still controversies around it, as the requirements for the importance of bibliographic activity depend on its scientifically sound solution.

Bibliography as a whole expresses the generality of bibliographic events in general; it performs a generalized character function, which in turn performs all the bibliographic features associated with coherence. This concept has the potential to be repetitive, repetitive, as well as internal infarct to others.

Bibliographic activity, like any other activity, involves two areas: practice and knowledge, the definition of which would be illegal only in part - practical. Consequently, a special concept is needed, which reflects the concept of “bibliographic practice”.

The bibliographer and bibliographic information and the bibliographer and distributor of its consumer represent the availability of the moment. However, the bibliographer not only affects the topic, but also the second topic - the interaction with the Consumer. Subject researcher in the field of knowledge - bibliographer, teacher and educator. Subject of bibliographic activity, as well as the presence of the subject of bibliographic activity in various bibliographic resources, maps and electronic catalogs (bibliographic manuals, reference books).

As an organic unit of sensitive practical and cognitive forms of bibliographic activity, their interrelationships should be emphasized. Practical activity is conscious; it focuses on the practical components of the ideal (in the form of knowledge, feelings, emotions, attention, focus, goals, objectives, goals, objectives). Moreover, in addition to conversion, on this basis, knowledge also fulfills the "criterion" of truth. Cognitive activity is not absolute: practice is included in it and in the form of learning objects and research funds.

In bibliographic cognitive activity, it is necessary to distinguish two subsystems: new knowledge is produced, which is retrained learning, educational, and informational. Both subsystems are closely related to bibliographic practice: first, to improve bibliographic practice through the search for new forms and methods; Secondly, it is related to professional training on the topic - this is one of the most important elements of the bibliographic process, without which the work cannot be done.

Educational and training manuals include elements of scientific activity (production of new knowledge) and elements of practical activity (participation in bibliographic processes). Practical activities have an impact in the fields of science and education. However, practical activities are also included in direct experience and informational experience (practical training) and mediation (included in the training materials published in the press, methodological materials). Thus, bibliographic practice is related to cognition in all its forms. At the same time, practical and informative measures are not seen; the latter is produced in practice and, according to its founders, encourages its development.

Bibliographic activity is considered appropriate; it is carried out in accordance with specific goals, projects, and programs. In the process of its development, there are some postulates, people are guided in action, and that is, there are clear principles.

Principles are the most stable, clear system of requirements for basic resource, content, organization, methods, and technology activities. They

differ in meaning. Most importantly, determining the level of quality of activities plays a large, methodological, methodological role. These include Principles of science, democracy, organization, and independent organization. Other principles are mainly related to cash, forms and methods of work, i.e. methodological and organizational in nature: objectives of the activity, objectives of the activity, content and methods of differentiation, systematic methods of work, change of systems, systematization compliance

For example, when the synergistic effects of self-development bibliography occur, such as bibliographic and primary data, bibliography is synthesized by providing a variety of knowledge. Genres of interdisciplinary nature are formed, in which different forms of metathetopes are combined - the interpretation of the main source. The bibliography refers to the functions of "Expert System" analysis, commentary documentary layer evaluation, and interpretation.

A synergistic approach to bibliography has not yet led to its proper development, but it promises to be very effective. It should form an independent functioning system with its own and specific functions and justify the formation and teaching pattern of bibliographic activities.

The guiding principle of the methodological nature that defines bibliographic events should consider the principle of event methods. Its essence is to achieve the necessary impact only when the methods and techniques used in each form of activity that meet the objectives. In the preparation of the bibliographic manual - it is a manual (self-education, training, scientific activity), taking into account the characteristics of the consumer (age, education, profession), accounting, taking into account the manual account. Bibliographic culture (beginner, intermediate, advanced, professional). Depending on these characteristics, a description of the selection, placement, location, documentary documentation equipped with auxiliary equipment is obtained.

The principle of binding means that it can be combined for bibliographic activities. This phenomenon is expressed through the processing of the bibliography into different branches, their composition into documents for universal processing. Bibliographic elements are included in various databases, uniting the author's document, work, distributor, consumer into a single database. This is done through a single bibliographic record that was created at the beginning of the chain and is invalid until its completion.

The integration that is taking place is also reflected in the level of scientific research, as well as in the tendency to strengthen interdisciplinary, interdisciplinary interactions. In this regard, it makes sense to talk about the separation of activities, but it is logical to talk about their convergence, the transition to each other in the activities in the border areas. The principle of binding is implemented in joint projects of bibliographic services at different levels, different agencies, and different agencies: in the publication of consolidated catalogs in the country or region; in creating a single automated information system. Bibliography combines the internal and external resources of libraries through access to electronic databases that are part of a global information system.

If seriousness involves the integration of all elements, the mutual arrangement of relationships, the ordering of functions, then the differences are put into different parts. The principle of differentiation in bibliographic activities is as follows:

Establishment of specialized information centers that perform specific tasks;

Distinguish in the practice of creating benefits (by industry, thematic, regional and other characteristics);

Catalogs and map files (traditional and electronic) for libraries and bibliographic services Original catalogs and maps.

The principles of integration and differentiation complement each other.

It is not true to list all the principles that govern bibliographic activity and produce in the process of its implementation. It can be divided in addition to the most common, basic, specific principles related to personal bibliographic processes.

The principles are clearly historical, operational in a particular society, and have changed in other contexts. At the same time, they retain important foundations, as it is directly related to the nature of the bibliography and its main tasks, which remain unchanged in different historical periods. The continuity of these functions makes bibliography exist as a mass phenomenon.

The principles of bibliographic activity are related to patterns. It is well known that this reveals another aspect of the nature of the phenomenon under investigation and the principles as the initial elements are their expression.

Level of use of tools.

If we talk about the principles of bibliographic activity, it should be noted that the most important of them, the most important of them, plays a role in determining the quality level of the activity, the methodological, methodological, methodological type. These include Principles of science, democracy, organization, and independent organization.

The analysis of bibliographic practical activity as a system is carried out, first of all, by its internal structure, definition of relations of its basic elements: the subject (carries out activity) acts with the purposes; Processes as relevant activities of the subject related to the use of material and spiritual forces; depending on the topic interaction; funds to achieve the set goals; Outcome (due to failure to achieve a goal or purpose). The main directions of bibliographic activity are:

Development and maintenance of library reference and bibliographic resources;

Formulation of various purposes and bibliographic benefits of students;

Bibliographic reference;

Information and bibliographic services;

Counseling and methodological work.

Organization of bibliographic activities of any live library:

1. aimed at prioritizing the library in this context;

2. Rational commission of centralization and centralization in the organization of library bibliographic service;

3. Availability of bibliographic services for all students (users), including services and products, including services and products in the prescribed legal order.

At the same time, the characters that reflect the most important features of bibliography as an object of regularization: purpose, theme, style, generality, social status, structure, time, material design, need.

An electronic document is a collection of data entered into the memory of a computer system designed for human comprehension using appropriate software and hardware. Electronic document collection and network:

Package documents These are electronic publications (classic literature, rare books, encyclopedias, optical CDs with databases, computer programs, etc.).

Network Documents This is text and other information provided on electronic networks that are installed directly on the disk. It can be changed.

Electronic publication - Electronic document (electronic document (electronic documents)), the final editorial and publishing is intended for distribution of unprocessed products without modification.

Database (database) - a set of data that is sufficient for the intended purpose and is presented on a computer-readable medium in a form that allows you to perform automated processing of existing data.

It is not enough to know the rules of use of the library to fully master the capabilities of the library. The modern philosopher M.A. LiftShitsa, "You may not know everything, but you may also know what it takes to move on to the knowledge you want." The library also provides readers with tools and methods aimed at the book fund. To do this, the library creates reference and search engines (SPA). Information retrieval is a tool to help libraries disclose the contents of a library and select books. SPA combines an electronic catalog and a traditional catalog, as well as the relevant electronic databases; the software provides the product to open the information space.

The capabilities of Electronic Catalog (EC), Alphabetical and Systematic Traditional Catalogs of Mixed and Regular Traditional Catalogs have undoubted advantages. An electronic catalog is a catalog of machine-readable libraries that operates in real time and is available to students. An electronic directory includes a multi-dimensional operational search at the same time. He asked for the functions of traditional catalogs: accounting, information and search. An e-catalog offers radically new search capabilities compared to traditional library catalogs.

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